

An Assessment of the Effectiveness and Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement Strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

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Abstract

This study examines the effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, focusing on detection, enforcement, and penalization methods, while exploring the factors influencing their success. In the first quarter of 2024, approximately 3,500 driver's licenses were confiscated in Region 2 due to violations such as driving without a valid license, non-compliance with the number coding scheme, and other infractions like seat belt violations, overspeeding, and reckless driving. Collaborative enforcement efforts, supported by local government rules, have contributed to a 15% reduction in traffic accidents and fatalities compared to the previous year. Employing a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design, the study surveyed 149 respondents across six barangays, analyzing data to assess the effectiveness of enforcement strategies and factors affecting their success. The results indicate that detection strategies, including police patrols and CCTV, enforcement strategies such as pedestrian safety operations, and penalization strategies such as impounding vehicles and ticketing, were rated highly effective. Additionally, factors like road user behaviors, vehicle safety standards, and road infrastructure challenges were found to influence the success of these strategies significantly. The findings, which were disseminated to local traffic enforcement officials, aim to improve traffic management and enhance road safety by addressing systemic issues, and infrastructure gaps, and promoting compliance through educational campaigns.

Keywords: detection, infrastructure, road system, road user, violation

Introduction

Approximately 3,500 driver's licenses were confiscated in Region 2 during the first quarter of 2024, reflecting an increase attributed to the LTO's intensified enforcement efforts and road safety initiatives. The primary reasons for these confiscations include driving without a valid license, non-compliance with the number coding scheme, and violations such as failing to wear seat belts, overspeeding, and reckless driving (Delgado, 2024).

In Region 2, the LTO, local police, and municipal traffic units collaborate to enforce traffic regulations. These coordinated efforts have contributed to a significant decrease in traffic accidents and related fatalities, as evidenced by a 15% reduction in road accidents compared to the same period in 2022 (Nepomuceno, 2024).

This study serves as a basis to assist in achieving uniform traffic enforcement and to bring awareness regarding the importance of compliance with traffic regulations.

Traffic Enforcement

Traffic enforcement refers to implementing and monitoring traffic laws to ensure road safety, minimize violations, and enhance order on roadways. In the Philippines, traffic enforcement is managed by local government units, law enforcement agencies, and organizations such as the Metro Manila Development Authority. Effective enforcement is vital in addressing challenges like road congestion and accidents (Torres et al., 2024).

A study on traffic enforcement in Dipolog City emphasized the importance of consistent enforcement of traffic laws. It found that enhancing road safety requires a balance of educational campaigns and engineering measures (Ferrer-Celicious & Naparota, 2023). In Ozamiz City, the lived experiences of traffic enforcers highlighted challenges such as non-compliance by motorists, adverse weather conditions, and limited public awareness (Paje et al., 2022).

Detection strategies refer to approaches used to identify and analyze potential threats, issues, or violations. In the Philippines, these strategies are applied to public safety, crime prevention, and cybersecurity. The Philippine National Police employs detection strategies to monitor crime hotspots and optimize response mechanisms. Technological advancements like neural networks are also used to detect public security threats (Ceballos et al., 2023).

A study by the Philippine National Police highlights how geographic crime pattern analysis and predictive modeling improve community safety through GIS to track crime data (Ceballos et al., 2023). Advances in artificial intelligence paved the way for automated detection strategies, with neural networks classifying security threats in real time, aiding law enforcement in identifying risks more accurately (Guillermo et al., 2020).

Enforcement strategies refer to approaches used by authorities to ensure compliance with laws and regulations. These strategies often involve policies, patrols, checkpoints, surveillance, and public awareness campaigns. The Philippine National Police employs checkpoints and community policing to enhance efficiency and safety (Adora et al., 2015; Patalinghug, 2020).

Adora et al. (2015) examined the effectiveness of the PNP Standard Operating Procedure for checkpoints and found it highly effective in deterring criminal activities. Patalinghug (2020) analyzed PNP crime prevention strategies in Salug Valley, finding that community-based operations and patrol systems significantly reduced crime rates.

Penalization strategies refer to the methods used by authorities to impose penalties for violations of laws and regulations, aiming to deter infractions and rehabilitate offenders. These may include fines, imprisonment, community service, or alternative sanctions. Programs by the Bureau of Corrections incorporate rehabilitation to reduce recidivism and prepare inmates for reintegration (BuCor, 2017).

Almoguerra et al. (2019) highlight anti-criminality programs in Quezon City, showing how penalization efforts combined with preventive measures reduce crime. A study on the Sablayan Prison and Penal Farm outlines its role in decongesting prisons and providing rehabilitation through work and education programs (Department of Justice, 2019).

Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement

An enforcement system refers to the structured approach and mechanisms implemented by authorities to ensure adherence to laws, regulations, or standards. In the context of road traffic, it encompasses policies, technologies, and manpower aimed at maintaining order and safety on the roads. In the Philippines, these systems involve manual interventions by enforcers and technological tools like closed-circuit television (CCTV) cameras for monitoring violations. Programs such as the "No-Contact Apprehension Policy" utilize surveillance technologies to record traffic violations, promoting a more efficient and corruption-resistant system (Aguja, 2020).

Harrison et al. (2019) emphasized that police enforcement systems combining visibility with targeted interventions, such as enforcement during peak accident hours or in high-risk locations, are most effective in deterring violations. They noted the importance of community trust in police to ensure legitimacy and acceptance of traffic enforcement activities.

The road user system refers to the interaction between individuals and entities that use road networks, including drivers, pedestrians, cyclists, and public transport users, as well as the vehicles, infrastructure, and regulations that support their activities. Effective management aims to minimize accidents, reduce congestion, and promote compliance with traffic laws. According to Hernandez et al. (2021), understanding the dynamics of the road user system is crucial for improving road safety, as it involves the integration of human behavior, infrastructure design, and regulatory measures.

Green et al. (2020) examined the role of human behavior in the road user system, identifying common risk factors such as speeding, distracted driving, and non-compliance with pedestrian crossings. The study found that individual behavior significantly contributes to traffic accidents and concluded that education and awareness campaigns targeting risky behaviors could help mitigate human error.

A road system refers to the network of roads, highways, and associated infrastructure that facilitate the movement of people, goods, and services. It encompasses the physical infrastructure and the organizational, regulatory, and technological elements that ensure safe and efficient road use. According to Jones et al. (2020), a well-functioning road system is essential for economic development, public safety, and environmental sustainability.

Brown et al. (2021) explored how different road system designs affect traffic flow and safety. They found that design elements such as lane width, intersection design, and alternate routes significantly impact traffic efficiency and accident rates. The study concluded that investment in better road system designs, including roundabouts and multi-lane roads, could improve road safety and reduce congestion.

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness and factors affecting traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, by examining their impact on traffic violations, accident rates, and overall road safety. The findings will contribute valuable insights to improve traffic enforcement strategies and develop evidence-based recommendations for policymakers and law enforcement agencies.

Statement of the Problem

This study assessed the effectiveness and factors affecting traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. This was conducted from August to December 2024 of the First Semester A.Y of 2024-2025.

Specifically, the study intended to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya in terms of:
 - a. Detection Strategies;
 - b. Enforcement Strategies; and

- c. Penalization Strategies?
2. What is the extent of the effect of the factors affecting traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya in terms of:
 - a. Enforcement System;
 - b. Road User System; and
 - c. Road System?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of factors affecting traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya?
4. What Education campaign material can be crafted based on the salient findings of the study?

Statement of the Null Hypothesis

At a 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis below was tested:

1. There is no significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of the factors affecting traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative approach using the descriptive-correlational method. The descriptive part was the survey on the level of effectiveness and the extent of the factors. Meanwhile, the correlational method was the relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of factors. The salient part of the study was Education Campaign material. The instrument used for gathering the data was a survey questionnaire.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in six selected barangays in the municipal center of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, situated at approximately 16° 31 North, 121° 11 East, in the island of Luzon. The six selected barangays include Poblacion South (819), Poblacion North (976), Quirino (6,405), Quezon (5,404), Osmeña (5,700), and Roxas (8,696), with a total population of 28,000 according to the 2020 census. These barangays were chosen due to their strategic location, vibrant economy, and dense population. The main streets included the national highway and several main roads that connect residential and commercial areas. These selected barangays are considered the commercial and urban hubs of Nueva Vizcaya, experiencing various traffic challenges that require effective management and enforcement strategies.

Research Respondents

The researchers used a purposive sampling method with a sample size of 149, which the panelists decided during the proposal defense. This consisted of thirty (30) drivers, fifty (50) passengers/pedestrians, fifty-nine (59) students, and ten (10) traffic enforcers with ages from 18 to 59. The researchers excluded 17-year-olds and those below because the age requirement for a

driver's license is 18. Hence, 18-to-59-year-olds are more knowledgeable about traffic rules and regulations making them more suitable respondents in this study. They are the selected respondents in this research, considering that they are the people who frequently go outside and use the highways. They have enough experience and knowledge of how traffic flows in the study area. The drivers always travel and they are always in the street, the pedestrians always walk and use the road, the students commute and walk every day to go to school, and the traffic enforcers do their roles and responsibilities to have a good traffic flow. Collecting data from 149 respondents was a balance between achieving meaningful insights and managing resource limitations.

Research Tool

The survey questionnaire provided was a systematic and organized set of questions to elicit responses from the respondents. This was a researcher-made questionnaire that contained four main parts. The first part was about the profile of the respondents. The second part was divided into three parts: Detection Strategies, Enforcement Strategies, and Penalization Strategies, which were designed to determine the level of effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The third part was also divided into three parts: Enforcement System, Road User System, and Road System, which were designed to determine the extent of the effect of the factors affecting traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The fourth part asked for recommendations for enhancing traffic enforcement strategies. It was piloted in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with thirty (30) random people. The tool was structured in the modified Likert scale on a 4-point scale in the level of satisfaction, ranging from "Very Effective" (VE), through "Effective" (E), "Slightly Effective" (PE), to "Ineffective" (I) and in the extent of the effect of the factors, ranging from "Very High Extent" ("VHE)", "High Extent" (HE)", "Low Extent" (LE), to "Very Low Extent".

Table 1

Reliability Test Result

Indicators	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha	Interpretation
Level of Effectiveness of Traffic Effectiveness Strategies			
1. Detection Strategies	5	.802	Good
2. Enforcement Strategies	5	.746	Acceptable
3. Penalization Strategies	5	.779	Acceptable
Extent of the Effect of the Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement Strategies			
1. Enforcement System	5	.745	Acceptable
2. Road User System	5	.892	Good
3. Road System	5	.859	Good

The reliability test results indicate that the detection strategies for traffic effectiveness are highly reliable (Cronbach Alpha: .802), while enforcement and penalization strategies are considered acceptable (Cronbach Alpha: .746 and .779, respectively). Among the factors affecting traffic enforcement, the road user system stands out with a high reliability score (Cronbach Alpha: .892), alongside the road system (Cronbach Alpha: .859), both categorized as good. In contrast, the enforcement system is acceptable (Cronbach Alpha: .745). Overall, most indicators show strong reliability, although some areas could benefit from improvement.

Treatment of Data

All data were organized and sanitized before being endorsed to a statistician, the researchers' quantitative data analyst, for the statistical analysis.

Frequency and percent distribution were utilized to identify the respondents' profile characteristics. The means, supported by their standard deviations, were quantitatively interpreted as indicated in Table 1 to describe the level of effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies and the extent of factors affecting traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya.

Table 2*Quantitative Interpretations of the Means for Level of Satisfaction*

Arbitrary Values	Mean Ranges	Level of Satisfaction	Extent of Factors
4	3.50 - 4.00	Very Effective	Very High Extent
3	2.50 - 3.49	Effective	High Extent
2	1.50 - 2.49	Slightly Effective	Low Extent
1	1.00 - 1.49	Ineffective	Very Low Extent

For testing any significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and extent of factors affecting traffic enforcement in terms of their profile, the Pearson r with test of significance was utilized for the statistical analysis since there is normality in the distribution of data gathered.

Results and Discussions

Section 1. Level of Effectiveness of Traffic Enforcement Strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

Section 1 highlights the consistent effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya—spanning detection, enforcement, and penalization measures such as police patrols, CCTV surveillance, pedestrian safety operations, and ticketing with fines—in fostering safer roads, enhancing compliance, and improving overall traffic management.

Table 3*Level of Effectiveness of Traffic Enforcement in Terms of Detection Strategies*

Detection Strategies	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Police Patrols	3.06	.72	Effective
2. Use of Traffic Cones and Barriers	2.95	.67	Effective
3. Undercover Officers	2.70	.80	Effective
4. Unmarked Vehicles	2.59	.82	Effective
5. CCTV surveillance	3.00	.82	Effective
Mean Rating	2.86	.57	Effective

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Ineffective; 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly Effective; 2.50 – 3.49: Effective; 3.50 – 4.00: Very Effective

Table 3 presents the level of effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, specifically focusing on detection strategies. The effectiveness of five strategies—police patrols, use of traffic cones and barriers, undercover officers, unmarked vehicles, and CCTV surveillance—was measured using mean scores and standard deviations and was generally found to be effective. Police patrols received the highest mean rating of 3.06, followed by CCTV surveillance (3.00) and the use of traffic cones and barriers (2.95). Undercover officers (2.70) and unmarked vehicles (2.59) also fell within the "effective" range. The overall mean rating for all strategies is 2.86, with a standard deviation of 0.57.

The overall effectiveness of these detection strategies suggests they contribute to maintaining traffic order and safety in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Visible measures like police patrols

and CCTV surveillance have an immediate deterrent effect, while lower ratings for undercover and unmarked vehicles may indicate a need for increased awareness or resources.

The result of the lowest mean score is similar to the findings of Pateña (2019). These effective detection strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya are due to the traffic enforcement programs and policies of government agencies, including the Philippine National Police-Highway Patrol Group (PNP-HPG) and the Inter-Agency Council for Traffic (I-ACT). Their strategies include deploying personnel, unmarked vehicles, and mobile units to target violations such as illegal parking and unauthorized modifications like LED lamps (Pateña, 2019).

The result of the second-highest mean score is similar to the results of Dela Cruz (2023). The LTO and PNP have partnered to enhance road safety and enforcement through technology, including RFID tracking and CCTV systems, allowing real-time monitoring and detection of violations (Dela Cruz, 2023).

Table 4

Level of Effectiveness of Traffic Enforcement in Terms of Enforcement Strategies

Enforcement Strategies	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Regulatory Enforcement	2.89	.67	Effective
2. Compliance Inspection	3.04	.64	Effective
3. Monitoring and Surveillance	3.06	.67	Effective
4. Saturation Patrols (Warn traffic violations through a visible and increased police presence)	3.08	.67	Effective
5. Pedestrian Safety Operations	3.15	.70	Effective
Mean Rating	3.04	.51	Effective

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Ineffective; 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly Effective; 2.50 – 3.49: Effective; 3.50 – 4.00: Very Effective

Table 4 illustrates the level of effectiveness in terms of enforcement strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Five enforcement strategies were assessed: regulatory enforcement, compliance inspection, monitoring and surveillance, saturation patrols, and pedestrian safety operations. Pedestrian safety operations received the highest mean score of 3.15, followed by saturation patrols (3.08), monitoring and surveillance (3.06), and compliance inspection (3.04). Regulatory enforcement scored 2.89 but still falls within the "effective" range. The overall mean rating is 3.04 with a standard deviation of 0.51.

The effectiveness of these enforcement strategies suggests they enhance road safety and traffic order in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The notable effectiveness of pedestrian safety operations and saturation patrols highlights their role in reducing pedestrian-related incidents and ensuring visible enforcement.

With the highest mean score, the PNP reported significant reductions in crime rates due to proactive measures, including enhanced patrols, monitoring, and surveillance, improving operational efficiency and public trust (Nepomuceno, 2024).

The LTO and PNP also enhanced coordination by incorporating technology such as RFID tracking and CCTV surveillance to improve vehicle monitoring and address traffic violations. These initiatives strengthen traffic enforcement and reduce risks like overloading violations (Dela Cruz, 2023).

Table 5*Level of Effectiveness of Traffic Enforcement in terms of Penalization Strategies*

Penalization Strategies	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Ticketing w/ Fines	2.97	.80	Effective
2. Filing of Case	2.61	.75	Effective
3. Suspending or Revoking Licenses	2.83	.82	Effective
4. Impounding Vehicles	3.07	.79	Effective
5. Verbal Warnings	2.79	.83	Effective
Mean Rating	2.85	.59	Effective

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Ineffective; 1.50 – 2.49: Slightly Effective; 2.50 – 3.49: Effective; 3.50 – 4.00: Very Effective

Table 5 shows the level of effectiveness of various penalization strategies employed in traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Five strategies were evaluated: ticketing with fines, filing of cases, suspending or revoking licenses, impounding vehicles, and issuing verbal warnings. Among these, impounding vehicles received the highest mean score of 3.07, indicating it is the most effective penalization strategy. Ticketing with fines followed closely with a mean score of 2.97. The strategies of suspending or revoking licenses (2.83), verbal warnings (2.79), and filing of cases (2.61) were also rated as effective. The overall mean rating is 2.85, with a standard deviation of 0.59.

The effectiveness of these penalization strategies suggests they play a crucial role in enforcing traffic laws and deterring violations in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The relatively high effectiveness of impounding vehicles and ticketing with fines reflects their direct impact on holding violators accountable, creating both immediate consequences and a deterrent effect. Strategies like suspending or revoking licenses and verbal warnings further emphasize personal responsibility, while filing cases ensures legal accountability for severe infractions.

In relation to the second- and third-highest mean scores in Table 4, the PNP-HPG is active in apprehending traffic violators, including illegal parking and operating without a proper franchise. Collaborative efforts between agencies like the LTO and local governments emphasize penalization strategies, including ticketing and revoking licenses, similar to the measures found effective in this study (Labalan, 2019).

The penalties provided by the LTO are stated in Department Order No. 2008-09, known as the *Revised Schedule of LTO Fines and Penalties for Traffic and Administrative Violations (2008)*. These cover violations related to licensing, number plates, equipment, weights and load limits, illegal operations, franchise conditions, frauds and falsities, traffic violations, and other non-traffic violations, with corresponding fines ranging from 150 to 50,000 pesos depending on the gravity of the offense. These penalties were later increased under Joint Administrative Order No. 2014-01 (2014) of the Department of Transportation and Communications (DOTr) and the LTO. The revisions raised the fines for licensing violations to 1,000–10,000 pesos, registration and operation-related offenses to 2,000–50,000 pesos, load limit violations to around 1,000 pesos, and franchise-related violations up to 1,000,000 pesos. These adjustments emphasize the government's intent to strengthen traffic law enforcement and promote compliance through stricter penalties.

Section 2. Extent of Effect of the Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

The research examined the extent to which various factors affect traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, focusing on the enforcement system, road user behaviors, and road infrastructure. Across all dimensions, the factors were consistently rated as having a "high extent" of

influence, with mean scores ranging from 2.73 to 2.86. In the enforcement system, vehicle safety standards and community involvement emerged as critical contributors, while behaviors such as cellphone usage and drunk driving impacted the road user system. Within the road system, road construction delays and outdated infrastructure were identified as key challenges. These findings emphasize the interconnected nature of enforcement, user behavior, and infrastructure in shaping traffic management effectiveness. Addressing these factors holistically can lead to improved traffic compliance, safer roads, and more efficient enforcement strategies in the municipality.

Table 6

Extent of Effect of the Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement in Terms of Enforcement System

Enforcement System	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Technological Advancement	2.68	.67	High Extent
2. Public attitudes towards Law Enforcement	2.75	.71	High Extent
3. Involvement of Community	2.76	.74	High Extent
4. Vehicle Safety Standards	3.00	.69	High Extent
5. Political Priorities	2.74	.75	High Extent
Mean Rating	2.79	.55	High Extent

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Very Low Extent; 1.50 – 2.49: Low Extent; 2.50 – 3.49: High Extent; 3.50 – 4.00: Very High Extent

Table 6 presents the extent to which various factors within the enforcement system affect traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Five factors were evaluated: technological advancement, public attitudes toward law enforcement, involvement of the community, vehicle safety standards, and political priorities. Among these, vehicle safety standards received the highest mean score of 3.00, indicating it has the greatest extent of effect. The other factors, including community involvement (2.76), public attitudes (2.75), political priorities (2.74), and technological advancement (2.68), also demonstrate a high extent of influence. The overall mean rating of 2.79, with a standard deviation of 0.55, indicates a consistently high perceived effect of these factors on traffic enforcement.

The high extent of the effect of these factors on traffic enforcement suggests their critical role in shaping the effectiveness and efficiency of enforcement efforts in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The influence of vehicle safety standards highlights the need for regulatory compliance to minimize road hazards, while community involvement emphasizes shared responsibility in traffic management. Technological advancements underscore the importance of integrating modern tools to enhance enforcement capabilities. The impact of public attitudes and political priorities suggests that societal support and policy alignment are essential for sustainable traffic enforcement.

The high extent of these factors is supported by government initiatives such as the Memorandum of Agreement between the MMDA and the LTO on advancements in data-sharing systems to improve traffic enforcement (Dela Cruz, 2022). In addition, the PNP's Operational Procedures Manual of 2010 includes guidelines on law enforcement practices, traffic management, use of technology, and public engagement, emphasizing community-oriented policing and adherence to human rights, aligning with the factors analyzed in this study.

Table 7

Extent of Effect of the Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement in Terms of Road User System

Road User System	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Distracted Driving	2.85	.79	High Extent
2. Drunk Driving	2.89	.86	High Extent

3. Inadequate Vehicle Maintenance	2.79	.79	High Extent
4. Cellphone Usage	2.90	.86	High Extent
5. Failure to Use the Right Way	2.85	.82	High Extent
Mean Rating	2.86	.68	High Extent

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Very Low Extent; 1.50 – 2.49: Low Extent; 2.50 – 3.49: High Extent; 3.50 – 4.00: Very High Extent

Table 7 displays the extent to which various factors within the road user system affect traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Five factors were evaluated: distracted driving, drunk driving, inadequate vehicle maintenance, cellphone usage, and failure to use the right way. All factors received high mean scores, with cellphone usage scoring the highest at 2.90, followed by drunk driving (2.89), failure to use the right way (2.85), distracted driving (2.85), and inadequate vehicle maintenance (2.79). The overall mean rating of 2.86, with a standard deviation of 0.68, indicates a consistent perception that these road user behaviors affect traffic enforcement efforts.

The high extent of the effect of these factors highlights critical road safety challenges in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Cellphone usage and drunk driving directly impact the likelihood of accidents and violations, while distracted driving and inadequate vehicle maintenance emphasize the need for stricter enforcement. Addressing these behaviors through awareness campaigns, penalties, and vehicle safety enforcement can enhance traffic safety and improve the effectiveness of enforcement strategies.

Laws and policies have been enacted to reduce the extent of these factors, including the Anti-Distracted Driving Act (RA 10913), which prohibits the use of mobile phones and other distractions while driving. The law applies to all motor vehicles and imposes fines and license suspension or revocation for repeated offenses. Research from government agencies such as the PNP and LTO also shows that cellphone usage and drunk driving directly increase road accidents and violations, reinforcing the need for stringent enforcement and continuous public education

Table 8

Extent of Effect of the Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement in Terms of Road System

Road System	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. Poor Road Sign	2.64	.82	High Extent
2. Lack of Pedestrian Facilities	2.72	.86	High Extent
3. Road Construction Delays	2.89	.82	High Extent
4. Outdated Infrastructure	2.81	.81	High Extent
5. Drainage Issues	2.59	.92	High Extent
Mean Rating	2.73	.68	High Extent

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49: Very Low Extent; 1.50 – 2.49: Low Extent; 2.50 – 3.49: High Extent; 3.50 – 4.00: Very High Extent

Table 8 presents the extent to which various factors within the road system affect traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The five factors evaluated include poor road signs, lack of pedestrian facilities, road construction delays, outdated infrastructure, and drainage issues. All factors received mean scores indicating a high extent of influence, with road construction delays scoring the highest at 2.89, followed by outdated infrastructure (2.81) and lack of pedestrian facilities (2.72). Poor road signs (2.64) and drainage issues (2.59) also reflected a high extent of effect. The overall mean rating of 2.73 with a standard deviation of 0.68 signifies that these road system challenges significantly impact traffic enforcement efforts.

The high extent of these factors suggests that infrastructure-related issues affect road safety and the effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies. Road construction delays and outdated infrastructure create hazardous driving conditions that complicate enforcement and increase accident risks. Similarly, the lack of pedestrian facilities and poor road signage may lead to unsafe interactions between vehicles and pedestrians. These findings emphasize the need for infrastructure improvements to complement enforcement measures and enhance overall traffic management.

In line with the results, road safety reports in the Philippines (Tupas, 2023) indicate that infrastructure-related factors such as outdated infrastructure and construction delays contribute to hazardous conditions, affecting traffic management and law enforcement efficiency. Recent reforms also highlight the importance of addressing road system issues, particularly infrastructure management, as road construction delays and the lack of pedestrian facilities hinder effective enforcement and safety measures (Gamboa, 2021).

Section 3. Comparison Between the Level of Effectiveness and the Extent of Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement Strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

The study compares the level of effectiveness of traffic enforcement strategies with the extent of factors affecting their implementation in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, revealing significant correlations between the two. Detection, enforcement, and penalization strategies were assessed alongside factors within the enforcement system, road user system, and road system. The strongest correlations were observed between enforcement strategies and the enforcement system ($r=0.395$), indicating the importance of systemic factors such as resources and institutional support. Detection strategies also showed significant relationships with the enforcement system ($r=0.392$) and road system ($r=0.244$), while penalization strategies had their highest correlation with the road system ($r=0.342$). These results highlight the interconnectedness of enforcement strategies and influencing factors, suggesting that strengthening institutional systems, improving road infrastructure, and addressing user behavior can enhance traffic enforcement effectiveness.

Table 9

Correlation Between the Level of Effectiveness and the Extent of Factors Affecting Traffic Enforcement Strategies in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

		Enforcement System	Road User System	Road System
Detection Strategies	Pearson Correlation	.392**	.224**	.244**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.006	.003
	N	149	149	149
Enforcement Strategies	Pearson Correlation	.395**	.256**	.259**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002	.001
	N	149	149	149
Penalization Strategies	Pearson Correlation	.243**	.285**	.342**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000	.000
	N	149	149	149

* Correlation is significant at <0.05 level

Table 9 shows the correlation between the level of effectiveness of different traffic enforcement strategies (detection, enforcement, and penalization) and the extent of various factors affecting traffic enforcement in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The correlations are statistically significant at the 0.05 level. For detection strategies, the highest correlation is with the enforcement system (0.392), followed by the road system (0.244) and road user system (0.224). Enforcement strategies also show significant correlations, with the enforcement system having the highest correlation

(0.395), followed by the road user system (0.259) and road system (0.256). Penalization strategies show the highest correlation with the road system (0.342), followed by the road user system (0.285) and enforcement system (0.243). All correlations are statistically significant, with p-values less than 0.05.

The significant correlations suggest that external factors such as road conditions, user behavior, and the enforcement system have a meaningful impact on the success of enforcement efforts in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The correlation between enforcement strategies and the enforcement system indicates that institutional and systemic factors, such as resources, policies, and political will, play a crucial role in making traffic enforcement more effective. The correlations between penalization strategies and these factors suggest that while penalties may deter violations, their effectiveness depends on road infrastructure and user behavior. These findings highlight the need for an integrated approach that addresses both enforcement mechanisms and road- and user-related challenges to enhance traffic enforcement effectiveness.

In the study conducted by Flieger and Susanj (2021), training was provided to traffic officers in the Philippines on best practices for speed enforcement and the use of advanced technologies like speed cameras. The study emphasizes that a combination of physical policing and automated enforcement strategies can enhance road safety. Additionally, a study on traffic management effectiveness in San Pascual, Batangas by the PNP in 2016 finds that traffic management is moderately effective but highlights areas for improvement in enforcement and penalization.

Section 4. Educational Campaign Material Crafted based on the salient Findings of the study

Following the completion of the study, the researchers coordinated with traffic enforcement officials to organize a conference for the dissemination of the research findings. During the conference, the researchers presented the findings and discussed the implications of the study, focusing on how the research could improve traffic enforcement practices through actionable insights and recommendations. A question-and-answer session was conducted, allowing traffic enforcers to seek clarification on the study's methodology and results.

As part of the dissemination process, the researchers distributed flyers containing a summary of the study's key findings and practical suggestions that traffic enforcers could implement in their operations. After the conference, comprehensive documentation was compiled, capturing the discussions, feedback, and recommendations made during the event.

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